

Eclipses

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An elementary geometrical description of eclipses is given. The described situations play a major role for sun- and moon eclipses.

Three balls are on a plane. Body 1 is a fixed star, meaning a self-radiating body.

a) Core shadow:

First we treat the core shadow. In core shadow, sun or moon are completely covered. We view two cases, that is, $R_1 \leq R_2$ and $R_1 \geq R_2$. We look at the following figures for both cases.

1) $R_1 \leq R_2$

2) $R_1 \geq R_2$

$$r_1 = \overline{M_1 M_2} \quad r_2 = \overline{M_2 M_3} \quad |r_x| = \overline{M_1 N} \quad |\cdot| = \text{absolute value}$$

With the similarity theorem we get the following result in the first case:

$$\frac{R_2}{r_1 - r_x} = -\frac{R_1}{r_x}$$

It follows with further rewriting:

$$-R_2 r_x = R_1 r_1 - R_1 r_x \quad \Rightarrow \quad r_x = \frac{R_1 r_1}{R_1 - R_2}$$

In the second case, we can use the similarity theorem, as well:

$$\frac{R_1}{r_x} = \frac{R_2}{r_x - r_1}$$

Transformed:

$$R_1 r_x - R_1 r_1 = R_2 r_x \quad \Rightarrow \quad r_x = \frac{R_1 r_1}{R_1 - R_2}$$

Thus, the same formula as in the first case. Now we calculate the angle α for both cases:

$$\sin \alpha = -\frac{R_1}{r_x}$$

b) **Half shadow:**

$$r_1 = \overline{M_1 M_2} \quad r_2 = \overline{M_2 M_3}$$

With similar triangles we obtain:

$$\frac{r_x}{R_1} = \frac{r_1 - r_x}{R_2}$$

Now we solve for r_x :

$$r_x R_2 = R_1 r_1 - r_x R_1 \quad \Rightarrow \quad r_x = \frac{R_1 r_1}{R_1 + R_2}$$

$$\sin \alpha = -\frac{R_1}{r_x}$$

We calculate the intersection points with the third ball. The boundary line of core- and half shadow are linear functions $y = mx + b$. m is the slope of the linear function. For both cases the following is valid:

$$m = \tan \alpha = \tan \left(\arcsin \left(-\frac{R_1}{r_x} \right) \right)$$

We obtain the line segment b with $0 = m \cdot r_x + b$:

$$b = -m \cdot r_x$$

Thus, we know m and b . Now we intersect the equation

$$y = mx + b \tag{1}$$

and the equation of a circle:

$$(x - r_1 - r_2)^2 + y^2 = R_3^2 \tag{2}$$

We can get two, one or no solutions.

The right choice of the solutions x_m, y_m :

We must take the smaller x -solution. This solution is called x_m . Then y_m is the accompanying y -value. In the case of no solutions, the whole third ball is in the core shadow space, respectively, in the half shadow space.

In case $R_1 > R_2$, it must be $x_m > r_1 + r_2 - R_3$ and $y_m > 0$ at the core shadow. Otherwise, the core shadow cone no longer reaches the third ball.

The size of the shadowed area:

The surface covered by the eclipse is:

$$O = 2\pi R_3 h \quad \text{with} \quad h = r_1 + r_2 - x_m$$

O is covered by the core-, respectively, the half shadow.

R_a = radius of the line of latitude (no geographical line of latitude)

R_r = radius of the distance, this circle is in the core-, respectively, in the half shadow.

$$R_a = \sqrt{R_3^2 - (R_3 - h)^2} = \sqrt{2R_3h - h^2} = \sqrt{h \cdot (2R_3 - h)}$$

We obtain for R_r :

$$R_r = \frac{2\pi R_3}{360^\circ} \cdot \arccos\left(\frac{R_3 - h}{R_3}\right) = \frac{\pi R_3}{180^\circ} \cdot \arccos\left(1 - \frac{h}{R_3}\right)$$

Circular measure: $\beta = \frac{\pi}{180^\circ} \cdot \alpha$

$$R_r = R_3 \cdot \arccos\left(1 - \frac{h}{R_3}\right)$$

In case of no solution, the half sphere that is turned towards the fixed star is covered. Then it is:

$$O = 2\pi R_3^2 \quad R_a = R_3 \quad \text{and} \quad R_r = \frac{\pi \cdot R_3}{2}$$

References

- [1] Harald Schröder "Trigonometric problem cases well solved" Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag Berlin 2001